

EFFECT OF PLYOMETRIC TRAINING ON VERTICAL JUMP AMONG FOOTBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of plyometric training on vertical jump of football players. In this study, 30 players from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur were selected as the subjects for this study. They were divided into two groups of fifteen each and assigned as control and experimental group. Experimental treatment was applied only to the experimental group for a period of six weeks. The control group was not given any treatment. The plyometric training was given thrice a week. After six weeks the final performance of both the control and experimental groups were taken. The significant differences between the means of experimental group and control group for the pre-test and post-test scores were determined by paired ‘t’ test. The level of significance was fixed at 0.05 level of confidence for the degree of freedom 1 and 14. It was observed that the experimental group showed significant improvement in vertical jump than the control group.

Key Words: Plyometric Training, Vertical Jump, Football.

Introduction:

Plyometric exercises train the muscles to effectively carry out the stretch-shorten cycle (SSC) which is a pattern of muscle contraction involving a stretch of the muscle followed immediately by an explosive contraction. Plyometric training is a method of developing explosive power and ultimately, improving athletic performance. Plyometric exercises include jumps, hops, skips, bounds and throws. Although plyometrics have long been utilized in athletic training and conditioning, the term did not begin to appear in literature until the 1960’s. Often an “innovative” training method such as this will be met with some skepticism; however, plyometric training has been adopted by coaches and athletes of all sports and disciplines from pure power athletes to team sports to endurance events such as rowing and long distance running. Research has shown that the combined effects of strength training and plyometric training can elicit greater performance effects than strength training or maximal power training alone and that plyometric training alone can improve maximal strength in athletes who have not previously participated in strength or plyometric training. The keys to achieving optimal adaptations from plyometric training are technique, progression, and periodization. Plyometric training is a highly specific training method designed to develop explosive power and to be implemented with a well-thought out annual training plan and in conjunction with other proven methods for improving explosive power (Matavulj et al. 1999).

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of plyometric training on vertical jump of football players. In this study, 30 players from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur were selected as the subjects for this study. They were divided into two groups of fifteen each and assigned as control and experimental group. Experimental treatment was applied only to the experimental group for a period of six weeks. The control group was not given any treatment. The plyometric training was given thrice a week. After six weeks the final performance of both the control and experimental groups were taken. The significant differences between the means of experimental group and control group for the pre-test and post-test scores were determined by paired ‘t’ test. The level of significance was fixed at 0.05 level of confidence for the degree of freedom 1 and 14.

Results:

Table 1: Computation of ‘t’- Ratio for the Mean Difference on Pre and Post-Test of Experimental Group on Vertical Jump

Experimental Group	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error of Mean	‘t’ ratio
Pre-Test	2.7109	15.8824	2.89972	3.737
Post-Test	2.7613	13.91039	2.53968	

* significant at 0.05 level 2.045

The table ‘t’ value for significant at 0.05 levels, with df 1, 29, 1.70 is 2.045 the obtained ‘t’ value is 3.737. The post test mean is greater than the pre test mean 2.7613, >2.7109. The ‘t’ value 3.737 is greater than the

table value of 2.045. It shows that that there is a significant development vertical jump of volley ball players at school level. This improvement in vertical jump of volley ball players due to six weeks training of plyometric training and stretching exercise.

Figure 1: Computation of 't'- Ratio for the Mean Difference on Pre And Post-Test of Experimental Group on Vertical Jump

Table 2: Computation of 't'- Ratio for the Mean Difference on Pre and Post-Test of Control Group on Vertical Jump

Control Group	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error of Mean	't' ratio
Pre-Test	2.6617	14.2066	2.59376	1.459
Post-Test	2.6677	13.0515	2.38287	

* significant at 0.05 level 2.045

The table value for significant at 0.05 levels with df 1, 29 is 2.045 the obtained t- value is 1.459 the post test mean is greater than the pre test mean $2.6617 > 2.6677$. The 't' value 1.459 is lesser than the table value of 2.045 it shows that there is no significant development in the vertical jump of sports school volleyball players in the control group since they have not undergone any treatment recently. The statistical analysis indicates that there is no significant improvement in the control group. The calculated mean value of pre test and post test of control group has no significant difference at this level.

Figure 2: Bar Diagram Showing the Mean Difference on Pre and Post-Test of Control Group on Vertical Jump

Conclusion:

It was observed that the experimental group showed significant improvement in vertical jump than the control group.

References:

1. Bosquet L and (2007). Comparison Of 2 Optical Timing Systems Designed to Measure Flight Time and Contact Time During Jumping and Hopping. Department Kinesiology, University of Montreal, Montreal, Quebec, Canada.
2. Bosquet L, et al, (2007). A comparison of 2 optical timing systems designed to measure flight time and contact time during jumping and hopping. Department of Kinesiology, University of Montreal, Montreal, Quebec, Canada
3. J Strength Cond (2009) Athletic Training Research Laboratory, Department of Kinesiology and Nutrition Sciences, University of Nevada Las Vegas, Las Vegas, Vada.
4. Matavulj D, et al., (1999). Effects of Plyometric Training on Jumping Performance in Junior Basketball Players. Research Center, Faculty for Physical Culture, Belgrade, Yugoslavia.
5. McLellan CP, et al., (2009). The role of rate of force development on vertical jump performance. Faculty of Health Sciences and Medicine, Bond University, Robina, Queensland, Australia;
6. Rubley MD et al (2009). The Effect of Plyometric Training on Power and Kicking Distance in Female Adolescent Soccer Players.
7. Rubley MD et al, (2009). The effect of plyometric training on power and kicking distance in female adolescent soccer players. Athletic Training Research Laboratory, Department of Kinesiology and Nutrition Sciences, University of Nevada Las Vegas, Las Vegas, Nevada.
8. Suresh, Kumar M. (2017). Influence of Yoga Practices on Blood Pressure Among Rural College Girls. Star International Research Journal, 5,1(3).
9. C. A. Vijayarani, Dr. V. Vallimurugan & M. Suresh Kumar (2012). Influence of Yogic Practices on Selected Physiological and Psychological Variables of Adolescent Boys. Recent Research in Science and Technology. 3,1.
10. Eswaramoorthy, A. & Suresh Kumar, M. (2020). Effect of yogic practices and aerobic training on flexibility among physical education students. Purakala, 31,8, 417-420.
11. Suresh, Kumar M. (2020). Investigation of the Changes on Selected Physical Fitness Parameters in Response to SAQ Training among College Women Students. Alochana Chakra Journal, 9, 4, 5121-5124.